
Herbivore-Mediated Plant Vulnerability: Rice Hopper Infestation Promotes Fall Armyworm Preference

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ABSTRACT

The invasive fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) poses a growing risk to Asian rice agroecosystems, although rice is normally a suboptimal host compared with maize. We show that prior infestation of rice by brown planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens*) or white-backed planthopper (*Sogatella furcifera*) reverses this host hierarchy, making rice highly attractive for FAW oviposition. In no-choice assays, FAW females laid 59–63% more eggs on planthopper-infested rice than on uninfested rice, reaching levels comparable to or exceeding those on maize. Dual-choice tests revealed that 48 h of planthopper feeding eliminated FAW's strong preference for maize, with damaged rice receiving equal or greater egg deposition than undamaged maize. In contrast, conspecific FAW damage on maize strongly deterred oviposition, reducing egg laying by ~45% and making maize less attractive than clean rice. Larvae and adults strongly preferred maize over rice when plants were undamaged, confirming that this shift is induced by planthopper herbivory. Together, these results demonstrate heterospecific facilitation, whereby planthopper feeding alters rice cues to exploit FAW oviposition plasticity, converting rice from a marginal to a preferred host. This hopper-induced vulnerability represents a novel invasion pathway for FAW and underscores the importance of early-season planthopper management to prevent secondary FAW

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most critical staple crops globally, serving as the primary source of calories for more than half of the world's population, particularly in Asia where it accounts for over 90 percent of global production (Fukagawa and Ziska, 2019) and consumption (Mohapatra et al., 2021). Rice cultivation faces numerous biotic stresses, including pests and disease that can causing significant yield reductions of 37 percent (Mohapatra et al., 2021). Among these, sap-feeding planthoppers and folivorous lepidopteran larvae represent two major guilds of herbivores that threaten rice productivity. The brown planthopper (BPH), *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål), and the white-backed planthopper (WBPH), *Sogatella furcifera* (Horváth), are monophagous pest's endemic to Asia (Kari and Dono, 2021), notorious for their long-distance migration and ability to cause 'hopper burn' a condition where severe feeding leads to plant wilting, stunting, and complete crop failure (Sogawa, 1982). These planthoppers not only extract phloem sap, reducing plant vigour and nutrient translocation (Yin et al., 2005). Brown planthopper not only causes direct damage to rice but also transmits viral diseases such as rice grassy stunt, ragged stunt, and wilted stunt virus (Wang et al., 2022), while white-backed planthopper (WBPH) is the vector of southern rice black-streaked dwarf virus (Zhou et al., 2013), together contributing to yield losses across rice-growing regions in the world (Wang et al., 2022 and De, 2025).

In recent years, the invasive fall armyworm (FAW), *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), has emerged as a transcontinental threat to rice systems (Mendesil et al., 2023). Native to the Americas, FAW was first detected in Africa in 2016 (Goergen et al., 2016) and rapidly spread to Asia by 2018, including China (Jing et al., 2020), India (Sharanabasappa et al., 2018) and Southeast Asian countries (Liu et al., 2024). While FAW is polyphagous, attacking over > 353 plant species belongs to 76 families including maize, sorghum, tomato, potato, peanut, tobacco, cotton, sugarcane, Johnsongrass, pigweed, morning glory etc. (Prasanna et al., 2018; Montezano et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2021 and Kenis et al., 2022) and its impact on rice has been sporadic but concerning, particularly on young seedlings where larvae defoliate whorls, bore into stems, and reduce tillering and grain filling (Kafle and Joshi, 2025). Yield losses from FAW in rice can reach 30-50 percent under unchecked infestations, with economic damages in Asia projected to exceed billions of USD if unmanaged (Day et al., 2017). The migratory behaviour amplifies its invasion potential, especially in intensified rice agroecosystems reliant on nitrogen fertilizers that enhance host suitability (Horgan et al., 2017).

A growing body of evidence highlights complex interactions among rice pests, where initial infestations by one herbivore can alter plant physiology, volatile emissions, and defense signalling, thereby influencing the behaviour, preference and performance of subsequent invaders. Planthopper infestations, in particular, induce jasmonic acid (JA)- and salicylic acid (SA)-mediated defenses in rice, reallocating photosynthates and altering volatile profiles such as methyl salicylate and decanal (Cheng et al., 2013). These changes can inadvertently create enemy-free space or attract secondary pests (Hu et al., 2020). For instance, BPH feeding disrupts rice root nutrient uptake, increases soluble sugars in foliage and emits attractants that draw lepidopteran moths for oviposition (Yin et al., 2005). Such facilitative interactions underscore a critical gap in rice pest management.

Emerging evidence suggests that prior herbivory by sap-feeding insects can alter plant physiology, inducing defensive responses or, paradoxically, increasing susceptibility to subsequent chewers. Hence, the present study investigates interactive effects of hopper infestation on fall armyworm preference and oviposition.

Materials and methods

A study on the behaviour of the fall armyworm was carried out using maize and rice as host plants at the ICAR-Indian Institute of Rice Research, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Insect culture used in the study

Fall armyworm larvae were collected from maize fields in Rajendranagar (geolocation: 17.328399°N, 78.386954°E) and reared on maize leaves in the laboratory until pupation. Pupae were placed individually in glass vials (4.6 cm diameter × 6.5 cm height) and maintained under controlled conditions ($28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $70 \pm 5\%$ RH, and a 10:14 h dark: light photoperiod) until adult emergence. The emerged adults were subsequently used for the oviposition preference study.

Further, emerged males and females (1:1 sex ratio) adults were paired and transferred to an oviposition cage containing 30-day-old potted plants (bearing 3–4 leaves) that served as the oviposition substrate. A cotton swab soaked in 10% honey solution was suspended by a thread inside the oviposition cage to serve as a food source for the adults. The honey-soaked cotton swab was replaced daily to provide fresh food for the adults. After oviposition, leaves bearing egg masses were excised and transferred to an incubation chamber. Emerging first instar neonate larvae from these eggs were used in cage experiment and larval host preference study.

The brown plant hopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* and white backed planthopper, *Sogatella furcifera* culture was maintained on TN1 rice at ICAR-Indian Institute of Rice Research, Hyderabad, Telangana were also used in the current experiments.

Plants used in the study

Two host plants, maize and rice, were used for the oviposition preference study. The maize variety DHM-117 and the rice variety TN-1 were selected (Fig. 1). For maize, 6–8 seeds were sown per pot, and well-established 30-day-old potted maize plants were used in the experiment (Fig. 1b). Similarly, 45-day-old potted rice plants were utilized (Fig. 1a).

Both BPH and WBPH infested rice plants were used in the experiments. Artificial infestation was carried out by individually enclosing each potted rice plant (variety TN-1) in a cylindrical mylar cage covered with 1 mm nylon mesh. Thirty third-instar nymphs of BPH and WBPH were released separately into each pot and allowed to feed on the plants for 48 hours. Similarly, FAW infested maize plants were used in the experiments. Artificial infestation was performed by releasing one neonate FAW larva onto each maize plant. The larvae were allowed to feed for 48 hours until typical scraping symptoms and small holes were clearly visible on the leaves (Fig. 2). After the infestation period, the infested plants were used for subsequent experimental analyses and all the plants were confirmed to be free from other pests and diseases before use.

Choice test for larval preference of FAW to maize and rice

Newly hatched first-instar larvae (≤ 6 hours old) obtained from the laboratory-reared fall armyworm culture were used for the larval preference study. Fresh, undamaged leaves of maize and rice were collected from potted plants. Both the host leaves were cut into 5 cm length and kept on the moist filter paper inside the petri dishes (15 cm dia.). One maize leaf section and one rice leaf section were placed opposite each other inside each Petri dish, ensuring that the leaf edges did not touch. Ten first-instar larvae were released gently at the centre of each Petri dish equidistant from both leaf sections using a fine camel-hair brush. The Petri dishes were then sealed with parafilm and kept under controlled laboratory conditions of $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $70 \pm 5\%$ RH and 10:14 h dark: light. The number of larvae settled and feeding on each host (maize or rice) was recorded 3 and 6 hours after release. Larvae present on the leaf surface or actively feeding (visible chewing damage) were considered to have chosen that host. Each treatment was replicated ten times.

Choice test for FAW adult settling on maize and rice

The settling (resting) preference of newly emerged fall armyworm adults for maize versus rice was evaluated using a dual-choice arena under controlled conditions. The experiment was conducted in large cages (90 cm × 90 cm × 90 cm) placed inside a glass house. One potted maize plant and one potted rice plant of uniform size and vigour were placed at opposite corners of each cage to provide a clear choice. Newly emerged 5 male and 5 female adults (≤ 24 hours old) from the laboratory culture released gently exactly at the centre of the cage floor, equidistant from both plants. A cotton swab soaked in 10% honey solution was hung at the centre top of the cage as a food source. The number of adults settled (resting) on each plant (leaves, whorl, stem, or underside of leaves) was recorded 3 and 6 hours after release. Observations were made with minimal disturbance using a red-light torch during the scotophase. Adults found on the cage walls, floor, or honey swab were recorded as “no choice”. This experiment was replicated ten times.

Fall armyworm ovipositional preference study under no choice condition

Newly emerged fall armyworm adults (≤ 12 hours old) from the laboratory culture were sexed, and one male–female pair was released into each oviposition cage (45 cm × 45 cm × 45 cm and top covered with fine 1 mm steel mesh for aeration). A single potted plant representing one of the five treatments (Table 1) was placed inside each cage as the sole oviposition substrate. A cotton swab soaked in 10% honey solution was suspended inside each cage as an adult food source. The cages were maintained under controlled conditions (28 ± 2 °C, $70 \pm 5\%$ RH, 10:14 h dark: light photoperiod). This experiment was replicated ten times. After introducing one adult pair of the respective insect into each cage, plants were observed daily. All egg masses laid on any plant part (leaves, leaf sheath, stem, or whorl) were recorded and the number of eggs was counted until the death of the female. These data were subsequently used for oviposition and fecundity analysis.

Fall armyworm ovipositional preference study under choice condition

The experiment was conducted under controlled greenhouse conditions using a complete choice arena to evaluate the ovipositional preference of FAW adults when in dual plant combinations were offered simultaneously.

Similar to the no choice experiment, newly emerged fall armyworm adults (≤ 12 hours old) from the laboratory culture were sexed, and two male–female pair was released into each oviposition cage (100 cm × 100 cm × 100 cm and top covered with fine 1 mm steel mesh for aeration). Dual plant

combinations representing one of the nine treatments (Table 2) was placed inside each cage as oviposition substrate. A cotton swab soaked in 10% honey solution was suspended inside each cage as an adult food source. The cages were maintained under controlled conditions (28 ± 2 °C, $70 \pm 5\%$ RH, 10:14 h dark: light photoperiod). This experiment was replicated ten times. After introducing one adult pair of the respective insect into each cage, plants were observed daily. All egg masses laid on any plant part (leaves, leaf sheath, stem, or whorl) were recorded and the number of eggs was counted until the death of the female. These data were subsequently used for oviposition and fecundity analysis.

Statistical analysis

The data from the dual host larval preference and adult settling behaviour as well as number of egg mass and eggs laid in the different treatments under dual host choice test were assessed by paired t-test. Whereas, the data on number of egg mass and eggs laid under no choice test were analysed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) based on Completely Randomized Design (CRD) was performed to compare the effects of five treatments with post-hoc comparisons using Tukey's HSD test.

Results

Choice test for larval preference of FAW to maize and rice

First-instar FAW larvae showed a strong olfactory preference for maize leaf volatiles over rice (Fig. 3). At 3 h after release, 8.2 larvae chosen maize and 1.8 larvae chose rice; at 6 h, preference increased to 8.7 larvae for maize and 1.3 larvae for rice). Preference for maize was highly significant at both 3 h ($df = 9$, $P < 0.01$) and 6 h ($df = 9$, $P < 0.01$). The attraction ratio shifted from 4.6:1 (maize: rice) at 3 h to 6.7:1 at 6 h. These results demonstrate that FAW larvae consistently discriminate in favour of maize and largely avoid rice leaf volatiles within the first 6 h of exposure.

Choice test for FAW adult settling on maize and rice

Adult FAW showed strong settling preference for maize over rice in dual-choice tests (Fig. 4). At 3 h post-release, mean numbers settled were 1.3 on rice (Fig. 5) and 8.7 on maize ($df = 9$, $P < 0.001$). At 6 h, values were 0.9 on rice and 9.1 on maize ($df = 9$, $P < 0.001$). Over 86 % and 91 % of adults settled on maize at 3 h and 6 h, respectively, confirming sustained and highly significant preference for the preferred host.

Fall armyworm ovipositional preference study under no choice condition

In no-choice oviposition assays, the mean number of egg masses laid by FAW females differed significantly among the five treatments ($F_{4,45} = 16.58$, $P < 0.001$). Females deposited the highest number of egg masses on rice infested with BPH (7.00) which was non-significant with rice infested with WBPH (6.90) and uninfested maize (6.50) (DMRT, $P < 0.05$). In contrast, significantly fewer egg masses were laid on uninfested rice (4.30) and FAW-infested maize (3.90) (Fig. 6). Similarly, total number of eggs laid by FAW was significantly different among five treatments ($F_{4, 45} = 147.32$, $P < 0.001$). Females deposited the maximum eggs on BPH-infested rice (962.5), which was on par with the WBPH-infested rice (950.6) and uninfested maize (938.5), with BPH-infested rice being significantly higher than the latter two (DMRT, $P < 0.05$). Whereas, uninfested rice (596.7) and infested maize (515.2) received markedly fewer eggs (Fig. 7).

Herbivore-induced rice plants (whether BPH or WBPH infested) increased egg mass and number of eggs laid by 60.46-62.79 % and 59.31-61.30 %, respectively as compared to uninfested rice, whereas prior conspecific damage on maize reduced number of egg mass and eggs by 40 % and 45.10%, respectively relative to undamaged maize. These results indicate that heterospecific herbivory on rice enhances its acceptability as an oviposition substrate for FAW, while prior conspecific larval damage strongly deters further egg deposition on maize.

Fall armyworm ovipositional preference study under choice condition

Dual-choice oviposition assays revealed strong and consistent preferences of FAW females for number of eggs and egg mass deposition that were markedly influenced by plant species and prior herbivory (paired t-tests, $n = 10$, $df = 9$). When offered uninfested rice vs uninfested maize, females laid significantly more egg masses on maize (5.4) than on rice (2.9) ($t = 11.18$, $P < 0.001$). Prior planthopper infestation of rice completely eliminated this preference (Fig. 8). In BPH-infested rice vs uninfested maize, females deposited similar numbers of egg masses (4.6 vs 4.2; $t = 2.45$, $P = 0.069$), and likewise in WBPH-infested rice vs uninfested maize (4.4 vs 4.3; $t = 0.56$, $P = 0.577$), confirming that planthopper-damaged rice became equally attractive to undamaged maize. Conspecific-damaged maize was strongly avoided. Females laid 3.1–3.3 times more egg masses on BPH-infested rice (6.3) than on FAW-infested maize (2.0) ($t = 28.15$, $P < 0.001$) and on WBPH-infested rice (6.1) than on FAW-infested maize (2.0) ($t = 41.00$, $P < 0.001$). Uninfested maize remained highly preferred over FAW-damaged maize (5.0 vs 2.1; $t = 29.00$, $P < 0.001$). Notably, even uninfested rice received more egg masses than FAW-damaged maize (2.6 vs 2.9; $t = 1.41$, $P = 0.192$), though the difference was not significant. Direct rice–rice comparisons

confirmed strong induction by planthoppers: females laid 2.7–2.8 times more egg masses on BPH-infested rice (5.3) than on uninfested rice (2.1, $t = 16.0$, $P < 0.001$) and on WBPH-infested rice (5.3) than on uninfested rice (2.0, $t = 17.00$, $P < 0.001$).

Similar to egg mass laid, when offered uninfested rice and uninfested maize, females laid 627.8 eggs on rice (Fig. 9 and Fig. 10) and 1145.6 eggs on maize (Fig. 11), showing a highly significant 1.82-fold preference for maize ($t = 9.86$, $P < 0.001$). However, prior infestation of rice with BPH and WBPH completely reversed this pattern. In BPH-infested rice and uninfested maize, females deposited 942.7 and 913.5 eggs, respectively, with no significant difference ($t = 1.82$, $P = 0.102$). Similarly, WBPH-infested rice and uninfested maize recorded 934.3 and 922.3 eggs, respectively ($t = 1.24$, $P = 0.247$), confirming that planthopper-induced rice becomes equally attractive as undamaged maize. Conspecific-damaged maize was strongly avoided. When BPH-infested rice was paired with FAW-infested maize, females laid 1328.8 eggs on infested rice but only 470.7 eggs on damaged maize ($t = 39.37$, $P < 0.001$) (Fig. 12). An even stronger avoidance of FAW-infested maize (449.9 eggs) occurred when WBPH-infested rice (1310.6 eggs) ($t = 50.08$, $P < 0.001$). Uninfested maize (1108.8 eggs) remained highly attractive when tested against FAW-damaged maize (455.4 eggs) ($t = 29.48$, $P < 0.001$). Remarkably, even uninfested rice (672.2 eggs) was preferred over FAW-damaged maize (684.8 eggs) ($t = 3.64$, $P = 0.05$). Direct comparisons within rice confirmed induction by planthoppers: BPH-infested rice recorded 1156.8 eggs vs 476.6 eggs on uninfested rice ($t = 63.47$, $P < 0.001$) and WBPH-infested rice recorded 1135.8 eggs vs 462.6 eggs ($t = 108.13$, $P < 0.001$).

The dual-choice assays revealed three key patterns: (i) Fall armyworm females strongly preferred undamaged maize over undamaged rice for oviposition; (ii) prior feeding by either BPH or WBPH fully negated this innate preference, elevating planthopper-damaged rice to a level of attractiveness comparable to, or surpassing, that of intact maize; and (iii) conspecific FAW damage on maize induced potent oviposition deterrence, making FAW-infested maize significantly less acceptable than undamaged rice. Thus, the number of egg masses followed the same hierarchical pattern as total eggs laid. Consequently, heterospecific herbivory by planthoppers converted rice from a low- to a high-quality oviposition substrate, whereas conspecific herbivory transformed the preferred host maize into the least favoured option.

Discussion

The recent spread of FAW across Asia poses a major threat to maize cultivation and could also endanger rice production (Acharya et al. 2022; Altaf et al. 2022). The herbivorous insect expands its host

range by overcoming the physiological and behavioural barriers (Gassmann et al. 2006). Plasticity often facilitates this process by enabling adjustments in behaviour and physiology to suit new environments (Portman et al. 2020). Some phytophagous insects go further by exploiting other herbivores feeding on the same plant. Similarly, our findings indicate a striking case of herbivore-facilitated invasion: prior infestation of rice by either BPH or WBPH dramatically increases its attractiveness as an oviposition site for the invasive FAW, elevating rice from a marginally acceptable host to one that is statistically equivalent to and in some choice, contexts even preferred over undamaged maize. Conversely, prior conspecific FAW damage on maize strongly deters further oviposition. These contrasting outcomes underscore the context-dependent nature of plant-mediated herbivore interactions in rice-based agroecosystems.

FAW larvae and adults exhibited a strong innate preference for maize over rice when both hosts were undamaged, consistent with the pest's association with maize under intercropping system (Tao et al. 2024; Prasanna et al. 2018). Under normal conditions, rice is a relatively poor substrate for FAW oviposition, larval settlement and showed low fitness (Hafeez et al. 2021; Altaf et al. 2022). However, just 48 hours of planthopper feeding completely reversed this hierarchy. In both no-choice and dual-choice assays, BPH- or WBPH-infested rice received as many or more eggs and egg masses as undamaged maize, while conspecific-damaged maize became the least preferred substrate, even less attractive than clean rice.

This facilitative effect aligns with earlier reports that phloem-feeding insects can increase the susceptibility of rice to subsequent chewing herbivores. BPH infestation suppresses jasmonic acid (JA)-dependent defenses while elevating salicylic acid (SA) signalling, leading to higher foliar soluble sugars and amino acids - nutritional changes that benefit lepidopteran larvae (Zeng et al. 2021; Zhou et al. 2009; Kuai and Lou 2024). Planthopper feeding also alters rice volatile profiles, often increasing emission of compounds that attract ovipositing moths of other species (Xu et al. 2005; Kuai and Lou 2024). The present study extends these observations to an invasive generalist, demonstrating that the same physiological alterations render rice highly attractive to FAW females.

The strong oviposition deterrence induced by prior insect (FAW) feeding on any host (maize) reflects a classic conspecific avoidance strategy (Reymond 2022; Carroll et al. 2006) widely documented in our current work on FAW. Herbivore-induced plant volatiles (HIPVs) from damaged maize, combined with physical cues such as frass, signal resource depletion and high competition risk, prompting females to disperse to alternative hosts (Dudareva et al. 2006; Karban et al. 2006; Arimura et al. 2009; War et al.

2011). In Asian rice–maize cropping systems, this avoidance behaviour may inadvertently drive FAW toward rice fields that have already experienced planthopper outbreaks - a sequence increasingly likely given overlapping migration phenologies and widespread nitrogen fertilization that favours both planthoppers and FAW. Although FAW populations collected from paddy fields initially showed low fitness on rice, their adaptation to this host can improve rapidly within a few generations, accompanied by phenotypic and genetic shifts linked to host use. For instance, larvae reared continuously on rice produced adult females that preferred to oviposit on maize during the first two generations, but by the fourth generation these females displayed a marked preference for rice over maize (Hafeez et al. 2021).

In a nutshell, planthopper-induced changes in rice transform a marginally suitable host into a highly attractive oviposition site for FAW, while conspecific damage on maize drives females away from their preferred host. These findings have direct implications for managing FAW in Asia. Early-season control of planthoppers emerges as a critical preventive measure to reduce subsequent FAW risk in rice. Over-reliance on broad-spectrum insecticides that disrupt natural enemies could exacerbate both problems, whereas deployment of hopper-resistant rice varieties (e.g., carrying *Bph* genes) or biological control agents may simultaneously limit hopper damage and FAW facilitation. Our findings point to the necessity of monitoring rice–maize sequential cropping, since FAW fleeing from severely infested maize may arrive in planthopper stressed rice fields, increasing the risk of intensified pest outbreaks.

This asymmetric interaction represents a novel invasion pathway for FAW in Asian rice ecosystems and underscores the importance of managing early-season sap-feeding pests to mitigate the impact of this transcontinental invader.

Author contribution

CBN Conceptualization, data verification, draft preparation and draft correction; RS Carried out experiment, data analyses and draft preparation; DDP data collection and data analysis; KAVS and AK Formal analysis and graphs preparation; KVS and RMS Draft correction. All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Statement

Not applicable

Data availability statement

All data supporting the findings of this study are included in this article.

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